

A STUDY ON EDUCATION SYSTEM WITH THE IMPORTANCE OF B.ED. DEGREE

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Abstract

The present paper explains that how important is degree for professional teachers. The quality of education in a country is a critical measure of the quality of its citizens. Teachers in secondary and upper-secondary education should have a Bachelor of Education (B.Ed.) that is usually a postgraduate qualification earned on the idea of a primary degree in another discipline. The professional degree checks the measure of quality of teachers and make a benchmark for them.

Keywords: Professional Degree, Quality Education, B.Ed., Teacher.

Introduction

Many school regions and states have since quite a while ago urged instructors to seek after graduate training. Instructors are every now and again allowed to utilize graduate credits for recertification, and educators with advanced educations by and large procure a more significant compensation or get a yearly stipend. Besides, now and again a graduate degree is a necessity for instructor licensure. As indicated by the 2015 information from the National Council on Teacher Quality, four states required a graduate degree or its proportionate in coursework for proficient licensure (Connecticut, Kentucky, Maryland, and New York), and four different states prescribe a graduate degree as a course to proficient licensure (Massachusetts, Michigan, Missouri, and Oregon). A graduate degree is likewise generally required for educator licensure in thirteen nations, for example, France, Spain, and Finland. Supporters have contended that graduate training may improve instructor viability and raise the status of the educating calling. The reason for this brief is to look at the pervasiveness of advanced educations among educators in the United States and to abridge inquires about on the connection between instructor instructive fulfillment and understudy accomplishment.

Many school locale and states have since a long time ago urged educators to seek after graduate instruction. Educators are much of the time allowed to utilize graduate credits for recertification, and instructors with advanced educations for the most part win a more significant pay or get a yearly stipend. In addition, now and again a graduate degree is a prerequisite for instructor licensure. As indicated by the 2015 information from the National Council on Teacher Quality, four states required a graduate degree or its comparable in coursework for proficient licensure (Connecticut, Kentucky, Maryland, and New York), and four

different states suggest a graduate degree as a course to profession.

Education in Republic of India has ancient tradition that dates back to the sacred text amount (1500 to five hundred BC). By the time European colonialists arrived, education largely materialized in ancient Hindu village colleges referred to as Gurukul, or in Muslim elementary and secondary colleges referred to as maktabas and madrasas. Land colonialists then obligatory education system supported land system and introduced English as a language of instruction. The primary establishments of upper learning in an exceedingly Western sense to emerge in British Republic of India were the University of Calcutta, the University Urban Center, and also the University of Madras, all supported in 1857 supported the model of British universities.

The British, wanted to unfold European science and literature and develop a loyal communicative manpower, recruited principally from India's higher categories, to administer its colony. They established education departments within the colony's provinces and discriminately disbursed funds in favor of English colleges teaching British curricula. On the eve of independence in 1947, Republic of India had seventeen universities and regarding 636 faculties teaching close to 238,000 students. Beyond question, land had altered the form of education in Republic of India, however they left the country with a grossly unequal and moralist system—a calculable eighty p.c to ninety p.c of the population was illiterate at the time of independence.

The period when independence was characterized by a fast proliferation of teaching establishments across Republic of India because the country tried to form a contemporary mass education system below the leadership of its 1st prime minister,

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Pandit Nehru (in workplace from 1947 to 1964). India's 1st constitution, adopted in 1950, required the availability of free public and required education for all youngsters till the age of 14-an objective that also eludes the state these days, huge progress in increasing access to education over the past seventy years withal.

India was established as a localized country with a federal system of state. Thus, India's states emerged as robust actors when 1947 and autonomously administered most aspects of education within the decades when independence. However, the central government of the Indian Union began to incrementally assume bigger responsibilities with the institution of establishments just like the federal office of Education, the University Grants Commission (UGC), instituted in 1953, and also the Central Board of education (CBSE), supported in 1962. In 1976, the constitution was eventually amended to form education the shared responsibility of the federal and state governments.

Review of Literature

Welling, (2013) But compared with the developed nations in the world, China is still in its infancy stage, and needs to learn from the western developed countries' experiences in this field. This paper makes a comparative analysis of the differences between China and UK in postgraduate professional degree education. It finds that there are significant differences between the two countries in the aspects of programme setting, schooling duration, admissions, curriculum design, teaching delivery, quality control system, etc. The findings imply that China should try to give more authority to universities in programme setting and admissions, and Chinese universities should innovate ways of teaching delivery and systems of quality control. Just like any other higher education program, applicants for teacher education must fulfill certain requirements and standards in each country. As we will come to know, in some countries teacher education is seen as one of the most important fields of study where as in others it may not hold so much prestige and value. In Kenya, there are currently five teacher education programs namely, early childhood development and Education (ECDE), secondary teacher education, technical teacher education, special needs education teacher education, and primary teacher education.

Mustafa Bayrak (2012) It is no secret that countries which have made adequate and appropriate investments in education are more developed than those which have not. Usually, the quality of education in a country is a critical measure of the quality of its citizens. According to the American

Commission on Teacher Education, the quality of teachers in a country largely determines the quality of its education system. This is to say that teachers play a crucial role in the achievement of the national education goals of any country. The teacher is the most important element in any education system because it is the teacher who is mainly responsible for the planning, implementation, and evaluation of educational activities.

Angelides, (2016) This thesis provides a comparative theoretical analysis and empirical description of teachers' Continuing Professional Development (CPD) in Abuja and Portsmouth. The theoretical sections comprise a comprehensive review of literature that examines teaching as a profession and key developments and the contribution of CPD towards teacher professionalization in both countries. The empirical aspect investigates and discusses the findings relating to teacher professional development, providing a comparative analysis of teacher profile and CPD in both countries. The aim of this research is to identify, compare and evaluate teachers' CPD in English and Nigerian primary schools, in order to explore any transferable best practices that can enhance the quality of teachers in an urban district of Abuja. It draws upon literature on comparative education research as an underpinning concept, and examines the peculiarities between the public and private primary schools foregrounding the unique context of urban Abuja.

India's Education System

Teacher education in Republic of India is overseen by the central government and falls below the ambit of the National Council for Teacher Education (NCTE), a statutory body that sets nationwide standards for teacher education schemes, together with course content, admission needs, and length and structure of programs. Solely academics UN agency hold teaching qualifications earned at NCTE - approved establishments are eligible to show at public and government-aided colleges. Teacher coaching programs are offered by universities and attached faculties and numerous alternative varieties of establishments, like complete establishments, governmental District Institutes of Education and coaching and Regional Institutes of Education. A directory of recognized establishments is found on the NCTE's web site.

Due to growing demand, the amount of teacher education establishments (TEIs) has exploded over the decades: Between one980 and 2013 the amount of TEIs grew from 1,553 to 16,181. Over eighty five p.c of those establishments are in private in

hand, and plenty of are aforementioned to be of substandard quality.

Observers like United Nations agency think about faculty education in Republic of India to be in disarray and beset by quality issues and unqualified academics. To handle such issues, the NCTE has created it obligatory for TEIs to get enfranchisement from the standard Council of Republic of India and recently introduced a TEI ranking system. Before then, the NCTE had delegated this task to the NAAC, however NAAC solely managed to accredit 1, 522 TEIs between 2002 and 2017. in an exceedingly sign of accelerating oversight, the NCTE late last year asked one,000 substandard establishments to stop operations, and more closures are probably.

The type of qualification required to show in Republic of India depends on the amount of education. Academics in time of life education and educational activity (inclusive of grade eight) should have a certification in educational institution Education (previously referred to as certification in time of life education), or a certification in educational activity severally.

Programs resulting in the subsidization of those credentials are entered on the idea of a grade twelve upper-secondary diploma; they're 2 years long, and embody twenty weeks of internships in colleges. Universities conjointly award the Bachelor of educational activity that qualifies those who've earned it to figure in body positions in education and provides access to more education-in addition to qualifying holders to show. It's not obligatory for elementary academics. The program lasts four years when grade twelve and includes twenty weeks of internships; four weeks within the third year of study, and sixteen weeks within the fourth.

Teachers in secondary and upper-secondary education should have a Bachelor of Education (B.Ed.) that is usually a postgraduate qualification earned on the idea of a primary degree in another discipline. Entry into B.Ed. programs needs a three-year bachelor's degree with minimum marks of fifty five p.c (or grade B), or a four-year bachelor's or master's degree. Till recently, these programs were largely one year long, however are currently mandated to be 2 years. B.Ed. degrees are awarded by universities and alternative choose establishments and embody a 16-week in-service teaching berth.

In addition, there are four-year integrated programs when upper-secondary faculty that causes double awards just like the Bachelor of Arts/Bachelor of Education and also the Bachelor of

Science/Bachelor of Education. The NCTE presently plans to form these credentials the norm in Republic of India.

Conclusion

Teacher degree and knowledge levels: Teachers' education (degree) and knowledge levels area unit in all probability the foremost wide studied teacher attributes each as a result of their simple to live and since they're, within the overwhelming majority of faculty systems, the only real determinants of teachers' salaries. However, there seems to be solely weak proof that these characteristics systematically and completely influence student learning.

In a 1986 literature review (and in follow-up reviews in 1989 and 1997) that has framed a lot of the talk, Hoover establishment senior fellow Eric Hanushek showed that solely satiny low proportion of studies realize these teacher characteristics to be statistically important within the expected direction.

Not all studies reach identical conclusion. in an exceedingly 1996 meta-analysis printed within the Review of instructional analysis, Rob Greenwald and his colleagues finished that "school resources area unit consistently associated with student accomplishment which these relations area unit massive enough to be educationally important" and "resource variables that plan to describe the standard of academics (teacher ability, teacher education, and teacher experience) show terribly sturdy relations with student accomplishment."

It's true in each set of reviews that a lot of studies found statistically important positive effects for teacher expertise than found statistically important negative effects; however the statistically important positive findings were found in mere concerning thirty % of the studies.

Part of the reason for the mixed findings is also that have professional and degree level matter solely in sure circumstances. As an example, there's very little proof that have on the far side the primary number of years within the room makes one a far better teacher. And teacher expertise implicitly captures the results of the rife graduation needs and market conditions at the time once academics were employed. Moreover, as I describe below, the result of degrees seems to ride the topics that area unit schooled and whether or not the degrees area unit specific to those subjects.

References

1. Agarwal, Nidhi and Sharma, Madhu, (2007). A Matter of Styles in Education. Asian Journal of Psychology & Education, 69(5), 2-6.

2. Agarwal, Nidhi and Sharma, Madhu, (2006). Environment Education Concern In India. University News, 44(12).
3. Angelides, (2016). A Collaborative Approach for Teachers' In-Service Training. Journal of Education for Teaching, 67(45): 12-23.
4. Borko, H., (2014). Professional development and teacher learning: mapping the terrain. Educational Researcher, 33(8): 3-15.
5. Cohen, D.K., (2016). Reform by the book: what is-or might be-the role of curriculum materials in teacher learning and instructional reform? Educational Researcher, 25(9): 6-14.
6. Kumar, Puneet and Agarwal, Nidhi, (2009). Reflection on the New Innovations for Maximizing the Learning in Teacher of Mathematics, International Journal Educational Herald, 38(2): 41, ISSN: 0974-0732.
7. Kumar, Puneet; Agarwal, Nidhi and Mishra, Sugam, (2010). Need to Acquire Democratic Competency by Teacher Educator in Global Scenario. Maa Omwati Journal of Education Research & Development. 1(1), ISSN: 0976-1365.
8. Leary, H., (2012). Comparing technology-related teacher professional development designs: a multilevel study of teacher and student impacts. Educational Technology Research and Development, 60(3): 421-444.
9. Mardis, A., (2012). From one to one to one to many: a study of the practicum in the transition from teacher to school library media specialist. Journal of Education For Library and In Formation Science, 48(3): 218-235.
10. Mustafa Bayrakc, (2012). In-Service Teacher training in Japan and Training in Japan and Turkey: a Company: a Comparative Analysis of Institutions and Practices. Australian Journal of Teacher Education, 67(41): 12-23.
11. Welling, (2013). Teaching with a peer: A comparison of two models of student teaching. Teaching and Teacher Education, 90(45): 9-12.